

Apparent molar volumes of L-glycine in aqueous glucose solutions at different temperatures

Amalendu Pal* and Suresh Kumar

Department of Chemistry, Kurukshetra University, Kurukshetra-136 119, India

E-mail : search@vidya.kuk.ernet.in Fax : 91-1744-38277

Manuscript received 22 April 2002, accepted 16 July 2002

Densities of L-glycine have measured at 288.15, 298.15 and 308.15 K in aqueous glucose solutions ranging from pure water to 25% glucose by mass. From these densities, apparent molar volumes and limiting apparent molar volumes of L-glycine in various aqueous glucose solutions have been evaluated. Transfer volumes and the infinite dilution partial molar expansibilities have been calculated from the temperature dependence of the limiting apparent molar volumes. The result are interpreted from the point of view of solute-solute interactions involving solvent effects.

The interactions of amino acids with water molecules in aqueous solutions of glucose and the temperature dependence of these interactions play very important role in understanding the thermodynamic behavior of biochemical processes in living cells. There are extensive volumetric and thermochemical property studies of aqueous amino acid systems^{1,2}, but few in aqueous glucose solutions³.

Here we report the partial molar volumes, transfer vol-

umes at infinite dilution, and the limiting partial molar expansibilities of L-glycine in aqueous glucose solutions at various temperatures.

Results and Discussion

The density data obtained at different temperatures for solutions of L-glycine in aqueous solutions of glucose are shown in Table 1. Apparent molar volumes V_{ϕ} ($\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$)

Table 1. Density (ρ) and apparent molar volumes (v_{ϕ}) of L-glycine in aqueous glucose solutions at different temperatures

m mol kg ⁻¹	288.15 K		298.15 K		308.15 K	
	ρ g cm ⁻³	V_{ϕ} cm ³ mol ⁻¹	ρ g cm ⁻³	V_{ϕ} cm ³ mol ⁻¹	ρ g cm ⁻³	V_{ϕ} cm ³ mol ⁻¹
			gly + water			
0	0.99910		0.99705		0.99403	
0.04949	1.00072	42.28	0.99862	43.31	0.99557	43.96
0.07558	1.00156	42.43	0.99944	43.38	0.99638	44.08
0.10209	1.00241	42.52	1.00028	43.42	0.99718	44.15
0.12339	1.00309	42.57	1.00093	43.49	0.99783	44.18
0.15163	1.00399	42.62	1.00180	43.57	0.99869	44.21
0.17289	1.00466	42.68	1.00245	43.64	0.99933	44.26
0.19666	1.00541	42.72	1.00318	43.67	1.00004	44.32
			gly + 5% glucose			
0	1.01948		1.01705		1.01385	
0.04812	1.02095	44.18	1.01849	44.82	1.01527	45.27
0.07403	1.02173	44.30	1.01926	44.85	1.01603	45.30
0.10021	1.02252	44.32	1.02003	44.93	1.01679	45.37
0.12666	1.02331	44.37	1.02081	44.95	1.01756	45.38
0.14748	1.02393	44.41	1.02142	44.97	1.01816	45.42
0.17604	1.02478	44.44	1.02225	45.02	1.01898	45.46
0.20184	1.02554	44.48	1.02300	45.05	1.01972	45.49

gly + 9.9% glucose						
0	1.03908		1.03632		1.03269	
0.04901	1.04054	44.59	1.03774	45.40	1.03406	46.42
0.07610	1.04134	44.64	1.03851	45.55	1.03481	46.48
0.10072	1.04206	44.71	1.03921	45.60	1.03549	46.50
0.12571	1.04279	44.75	1.03991	45.69	1.03617	46.58
0.15299	1.04358	44.81	1.04068	45.72	1.03691	46.64
0.17498	1.04421	44.87	1.04129	45.77	1.03750	46.70
0.20203	1.04499	44.90	1.04204	45.82	1.03823	46.73
gly + 14.8% glucose						
0	1.05960		1.05659		1.05333	
0.05005	1.06104	45.16	1.05800	45.75	1.05468	46.90
0.07596	1.06178	45.19	1.05872	45.84	1.05537	46.97
0.10122	1.06250	45.20	1.05942	45.88	1.05604	47.02
0.12617	1.06321	45.21	1.06011	45.91	1.05670	47.04
0.14963	1.06387	45.25	1.06075	45.96	1.05732	47.06
0.17590	1.06461	45.27	1.06147	45.99	1.05801	47.08
0.20232	1.06535	45.29	1.06219	46.01	1.05870	47.11
gly + 20% glucose						
0	1.08113		1.07783		1.07428	
0.04989	1.08252	45.54	1.07919	46.13	1.07553	48.11
0.07598	1.08324	45.59	1.07989	46.22	1.07618	48.13
0.09974	1.08389	45.65	1.08053	46.23	1.07677	48.14
0.12627	1.08461	45.71	1.08124	46.26	1.07743	48.15
0.15160	1.08530	45.73	1.08191	46.31	1.07805	48.16
0.17377	1.08590	45.75	1.08249	46.36	1.07859	48.19
0.19457	1.08646	45.77	1.08304	46.38	1.07910	48.20
gly + 24.9% glucose						
0	1.10281		1.09913		1.09533	
0.04834	1.10418	44.71	1.10049	44.96	1.09664	45.89
0.07506	1.10493	44.76	1.10123	45.05	1.09736	45.91
0.09913	1.10560	44.82	1.10190	45.06	1.09800	45.97
0.12252	1.10625	44.85	1.10254	45.12	1.09862	46.02
0.15033	1.10702	44.87	1.10329	45.22	1.09935	46.08
0.17431	1.10768	44.90	1.10394	45.26	1.09998	46.11
0.19922	1.10836	44.94	1.10461	45.30	1.10063	46.14

were calculated from these data using eqn. (1)⁴,

$$V_{\phi} = M/\rho - 1000(\rho - \rho_0)/m\rho\rho_0 \quad (1)$$

where m is the molality (mol kg^{-1}) of the solution, M the relative molar mass of the solute (g mol^{-1}), and ρ_0 and ρ are the densities (g cm^{-3}) of solvent and solute, respectively. The resulting values of the apparent molar volumes (V_{ϕ}), and the molal concentrations (m) of L-glycine in aqueous glucose solutions at 288.15, 298.15, and 308.15 K are also reported in Table 1. Values of V_{ϕ} can be fitted by eqn. (2),

$$V_{\phi} = V_{\phi}^0 + S_{\vee}^* m \quad (2)$$

The limiting value, V_{ϕ}^0 , of the apparent molar volume can be regarded as the infinite dilution partial molar volume (V^0). S_{\vee}^* , the slope indicates solute-solute interaction arising from glucose solution concentration effects. The values of V_{ϕ}^0 and S_{\vee}^* have been evaluated by computerized least-squares fitting to eqn. (2) and are listed in Table 2 along with the corresponding values of average standard deviations. There is good agreement between V_{ϕ}^0 values in water

Table 2. Limiting apparent molar volumes (V_ϕ^0) and experimental slopes (S_V^*) for L-glycine in aqueous glucose solutions at different temperatures

Glucose mass %	Temp. K	V_ϕ^0 *		S_V^* cm ³ L ^{1/2} mol ^{-3/2}	Stand. dev.
		Expt. cm ³ mol ⁻¹	Lit.		
0	288.15	42.20 (42.29 ^a)		2.81	0.02
	298.15	43.19 (43.15 ^c , 43.20 ^d)	43.19 ^{a,b}	2.54	0.02
	308.15	43.89 (43.81 ^a)		2.19	0.01
5	288.15	44.13		1.78	0.03
	298.15	44.75		1.50	0.02
	308.15	45.20		1.45	0.02
9.9	288.15	44.49		2.10	0.01
	298.15	45.33		2.57	0.03
	308.15	46.31		2.13	0.02
14.8	288.15	45.12		0.85	0.01
	298.15	45.70		1.64	0.02
	308.15	46.87		1.26	0.01
20	288.15	45.48		1.61	0.01
	298.15	46.07		1.62	0.03
	308.15	48.08		0.60	0.01
24.9	288.15	44.66		1.45	0.02
	298.15	44.86		2.28	0.03
	308.15	45.79		1.79	0.01

* Literature value in parenthesis : ^aRef. 5, ^bRef. 2, ^cRef. 6, ^dRef. 7.

for L-glycine obtained in this work and those reported in the literature^{2,5-7} (Table 2).

The partial molar volumes of a solute at infinite dilution reflect the effects of solute-solvent interactions while the magnitude of the slope is related to the solute-solute interactions. As can be seen from Table 2 that the values of the slope are positive, suggesting solute-solute interactions in the system. The slope decreases with increasing temperature at 5 and 20 mass % of glucose. This is reflected to the decreased solute-solute interactions, that is, the maximum breaking of the glucose structure on addition of L-glycine takes place both on increasing mass % of glucose and increasing temperature. Whereas at 9.9 and 14.8 mass % of glucose, the S_V^* values increased, and again decreased as the temperature was increased. An increase of temperature may enhance L-glycine-glucose physical interactions. After 20 mass % of glucose, the values of the slope increases from 288.15 to 298.15 K, indicating the structure-making effect of L-glycine in the glucose-rich region. So it is found that in the range 5–20 mass % of glucose, L-glycine is more effective as a structure-breaker.

Table 2 shows that the limiting apparent molar volumes (V_ϕ^0) values are positive and increase with increasing glucose content in solution as well as with increasing temperature upto 20 mass % of glucose. This suggests the strong solute-solvent interactions in the mixtures.

Transfer volumes of L-glycine, ΔV_ϕ^0 from water to aqueous glucose solutions at infinite dilution are calculated from eqn. (3),

$$\Delta V_\phi^0 = V_\phi^0 \text{ (in aq. glucose soln.)} - V_\phi^0 \text{ (in water)} \quad (3)$$

The results are illustrated in Fig. 1. It can be found that transfer volumes of L-glycine are positive and increase with increasing mass percentage of glucose in solutions. This suggests that L-glycine is a structure-breaker in aqueous

Fig. 1. Transfer volumes ΔV_ϕ^0 of L-glycine against mass % of glucose at (O) 288.15, (Δ) 298.15 and (□) 308.15 K.

glucose solutions. This structure-breaking effects increases with increasing glucose content in solutions. Upto 24.9 mass % of glucose, transfer volumes of L-glycine are positive, first increasing and then decreasing. This means that L-glycine is an effective structure-breaker in the water-rich region. The maximum in ΔV_ϕ^0 value at 20 mass % of glucose indicates maximum breaking of the cyclic structure of glucose on addition of L-glycine. After 20 mass % of glucose, the transfer volumes becomes decreasing, indicating the structure-making effect of L-glycine in the higher mass % region of glucose. Again, it is found that in the range 9.9–24.9 mass % of glucose, the transfer volume of L-glycine decreases and then increases with increasing temperatures. In the 20 mass % of glucose, the magnitude of ΔV_ϕ^0 is higher. In lower concentration range of glucose (9.9 mass %), the interaction of water with glucose is not so strong and does not involve any structural changes. It appears that, at small percentage, L-glycine might be behaving as a strong struc-

ture-breaker and at higher percentages as a structure-maker solute.

The variation of V_{ϕ}^0 with temperature can be expressed as

$$V_{\phi}^0 = A + B T + C T^2 \quad (4)$$

where T is the temperature in degrees Kelvin.

The partial molar expansibilities at infinite dilution can be obtained by differentiating eqn. (3) with respect to temperature,

$$\phi_{\text{L}}^0 = (\partial V_{\phi}^0 / \partial T)_{\text{p}} = B + 2 CT \quad (5)$$

The ϕ_{L}^0 values of the L-glycine at 288.15, 298.15 and 308.15 K are recorded in Table 3. It may be noted that the ϕ_{L}^0 value of L-glycine decreases with rising temperature upto 5 mass % of glucose solution indicating maximum structure-breaking of glucose on addition of L-glycine. When the concentration of glucose is higher than 5 mass % the ϕ_{L}^0 values of L-glycine increases with increasing temperature. At high concentration of glucose and at low temperature, the ϕ_{L}^0 values are negative, favoring solute-solvent interactions. The effect is that charged end-group of L-glycine influences electrostatically surrounding water molecules, so called electrostriction. As a result, the electrostricted water may be released from the loose solvation layers of L-glycine by the elevation of temperature. The effect is that the removal of water molecules favors L-glycine-glucose intercalations, indicating the structure-breaking effect of L-glycine in the high concentration region of glucose (maximum at 20 mass % of glucose) and at high temperature.

Table 3 Limiting partial molar expansibilities (ϕ_{L}^0) of L-glycine in aqueous glucose solution at different temperatures

Glucose mass %	$\phi_{\text{L}}^0, \text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$		
	288 15 K	298 15 K	308 15 K
0	0 113	0 084	0 055
5	0 070	0 053	0 036
9 9	0 077	0 091	0 105
14 8	0 028	0 087	0 146
20	-0 012	0 130	0 272
24 9	-0 017	0 056	0 129

The concentration dependence of S_{V}^* values of L-glycine in aqueous glucose solutions has been interpreted in terms of the solute-solute interactions. Unfortunately, the variation of S_{V}^* with temperature or the mass % of glucose (Table 2) shows some scatters. This may be due to relatively low accuracy in density measurements with pycnometer, and hence we could not obtain very credible values of S_{V}^* to give

a detailed discussion.

Experimental

L-Glycine (A.R.) was crystallized twice from ethanol-water mixture. The material was used after drying at 100° for 6 h and then under vacuum over silica gel at room temperature for a minimum of 24 h. D-Glucose (A.R.) was dried under vacuum at 50° and kept in vacuum dessicator for a minimum of 24 h before use. Water used in these experiments was deionized and distilled, and was degassed prior to making solutions. Solutions of glucose were prepared by mass in the range 5–25% by 5% increments. Solutions of L-glycine were made by mass on the molality concentration scale with an accuracy of $\pm 1 \times 10^{-4}$ g, and stored in sealable bottles prior to use. Uncertainties in solution concentrations were estimated at $\pm 2 \times 10^{-5}$ mol kg⁻¹ in calculations.

Solution density was measured with a pycnometer having a total volume about 8 cm³ with a graduated stem of 0.05 cm³ divisions. The pycnometer was calibrated at 288.15, 298.15 and 308.15 K with water⁸ which was filled to the marks on the stem. Its working was checked by measuring the densities of aqueous NaCl solutions at 298 15 K and good agreement was found with the literature values^{4,9}. The mass of the dried pycnometer alongwith a teflon cap was first taken. Subsequently, the test solution was introduced into it by means of a hypodermic syringe, taking care that no air bubble was entrapped. The limb of the pycnometer was then closed with teflon cap and weighed. The pycnometer with the test solution was equilibrated in a water-bath (± 0.01 K) of the desired temperature until no further change in the level of the solution in the capillary was observed. This level was noted and used in the calculation of density. Further readings on the same solution were taking at the other two lower temperatures, achieved by putting the pycnometer in two separate baths maintained at the required temperatures. The evaporation losses remained insignificant during the time of actual measurements. The reproducibility in the density measurements was better than 3×10^{-5} g cm⁻³.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (S.K.) is thankful to the University authorities for awarding a University Research Fellowship.

References

- 1 M M Duke, A W Hakim, R M McKay and K E Preuss. *Can J Chem*, 1994, **72**, 1489. A W Hakim, M M Duke, S A Klassen, R M McKay and K E Preuss. *Can J Chem*, 1994, **72**, 362, D P Kharakoz, *Biophys Chem*, 1989, **34**, 115 *J Phys Chem*, 1991, **95**, 5634

2. F. J. Millero, A. L. Surdo and C. Shin, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1978, **82**, 784.
3. X. Wei, X. Hu, S. Shao, R. Lin and S. Li, *Thermochim. Acta*, 2000, **362**, 1.
4. F. J. Millero, "In Structure and Transport Process in Water and Aqueous Solutions", ed. R. A. Horne, Wiley, New York, 1972, Chap. 12.
5. M. Kikuchi, M. Sakurai and K. Nitta, *J. Chem. Eng. Data*, 1995, **40**, 935.
6. T. S. Banipal, G. Singh and B. S. Lark, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2000, **39**, 1011.
7. T. V. Chalikian, A. P. Savazyan and K. J. Breslauer, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1993, **97**, 13017.
8. G. S. Kell, *J. Chem. Eng. Data*, 1975, **20**, 97.
9. F. Vaslow, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1966, **70**, 2286.